

WHO
Strategic Advisory Group
on Malaria Eradication

Working papers

Group 1: Potential economic benefits of malaria elimination and eradication

Title

The malaria elimination game

Author

Scott Barrett (Columbia University)

Contact

sb3116@columbia.edu

This working paper was commissioned by the WHO Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication between 2016 and 2019.

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The Malaria Elimination Game

Scott Barrett
Columbia University

Preliminary draft
18 November 2018

Abstract. Sometime in the future, possibly within a few years, the nations of the world will meet in Geneva to decide whether or not to declare a goal to eradicate malaria, a disease that currently puts about half of the world's population at risk, that causes over 200 million cases of infection a year, and that kills over 400,000 people annually, mainly young children in sub-Saharan Africa. This paper, still preliminary, develops a model to investigate the incentives that individuals have to protect themselves from malaria, and that nation states have to control and eliminate malaria unilaterally. (In the future I can incorporate an analysis of the incentives all countries together have to eradicate malaria worldwide.) The paper builds on the classic Ross-Macdonald epidemiology model of the dynamics of transmission within and between mosquito and human host populations, and allows the players (individuals at the local/national level; in subsequent work, this could be extended to nation states at the regional/global level) to choose their control actions. As malaria control abounds with externalities, and as the conditions that shape behavior vary widely around the world, this model should be helpful in identifying the challenges that must be overcome in pursuit of this audacious goal.

1. Introduction

When the Global Malaria Eradication Program was launched in 1955, its success was far from certain. Critics thought that elimination would be difficult in areas with poor health systems. They also expressed concern that, should eradication fail, and efforts to eliminate malaria be scaled back, individuals who had lost immunity in the interim period, thanks to the program's success, would be at risk from a resurgence (Nájera, González-Silva, and Alonso 2011: 2). Despite these warnings, the program succeeded spectacularly in some places in the early years. In Sri Lanka, for example, incidence fell from around one million cases a year to just 17 cases in 1963. However, just as it seemed that malaria was about to be eliminated in Sri Lanka, the case count there started to increase, and by 1969 there were once again over half a million cases on the island. It was also at this time that the entire global effort was suspended, with the operational goal switching from eradication to control.

For decades after this, transmission of malaria in Sri Lanka and elsewhere remained high, with malaria deaths nearly doubling between 1980 and 2004 (Murray et al. 2012). Starting around 2000, however, the situation started to reverse, and malaria

seemed once again in retreat in the face of determined public action.¹ The gains were greatest in Africa, a continent that had been neglected by the previous eradication campaign. By 2015, prevalence of *P. falciparum*, the deadliest form of malaria, had been cut in half in Africa (Bhatt et al. 2015). Elsewhere, the map of malaria endemic countries was shrinking (Feachem et al. 2010). Against the background of these positive trends, Bill and Melinda Gates declared in 2007 that the world should recommit itself to the goal of eradicating malaria. Some years from now, the World Health Assembly will consider their challenge.

Should the world try again to eradicate malaria? In his speech calling for malaria eradication, Bill Gates said, “We should declare the goal of eradicating malaria because we can eradicate malaria.”² In truth, however, we’ll never know if we *can* eradicate malaria unless and until we *do* eradicate malaria. Polio has been on the cusp of eradication for more than a decade, and still it isn’t 100% certain that polio can be eradicated. The feasibility of eradication is a prerequisite for pursuing the goal of eradication; it shouldn’t be the *reason* for pursuing this goal. The reason for pursuing eradication should be the belief that, by doing so, the world would be better off. This places the question posed at the start of this paragraph in the realm of cost-benefit analysis.

A number of key features of eradication must be reflected in a cost-benefit analysis of the decision to eradicate. First, the reason for eradicating a disease isn’t only to eliminate infections; it is also—perhaps even mainly—to avoid the need to control the disease in the future. Hence, a key component of a cost-benefit analysis is identification of the alternative to eradication: the level of “optimal control,” and this needn’t be the current level of control. Second, eradication may prove unattainable for many reasons. It’s impossible to know how a complex system involving humans, vectors, and pathogens will play out as it is pushed into completely uncharted territory. A benefit-cost analysis of eradication needs to incorporate the probability that eradication will succeed. Third, analysis must also address the post-eradication risks. For example, if the four species of parasite that currently infect humans are eradicated, might another species evolve to fill the opened niche? What actions are needed to guard against the risk of re-emergence? Finally, many of the tools deployed to control malaria are prone to resistance, and the risks of resistant strains emerging and spreading increase as control methods are stepped up, as is needed if the goal is to eradicate. The risk of failure may thus not be that the world will revert to the level of control that is optimal today. Resistance fueled by an attempt to eradicate malaria may mean that this level of control is no longer attainable.

An allied set of issues concerns the incentives individuals in malaria endemic countries have to stamp out transmission, even when the risk to them of being infected is very low; the incentives endemic countries have to pursue elimination

¹ Snow et al. (2017) find that the cycles and trends in malaria prevalence over the last 115 years can’t be explained by deliberate intervention or underlying trends like climate change.

² <https://www.gatesfoundation.org/media-center/speeches/2007/10/bill-gates-malaria-forum>.

within their jurisdictions, even as malaria continues to enter the country from outside; and the incentives all countries together have to see the enterprise through to completion.

This paper is a preliminary inquiry into these issues. I am unable to address all of these matters here. In particular, I ignore the problem of resistance. I also ignore the spatial aspects of control/elimination possibly leading to eradication. (If funding were available, I would be interested in taking up these subjects and perhaps others in future work.)

There is an enormous literature on the mathematics of malaria transmission. The novelty in my analysis is that it incorporates human behavior. This is especially important because malaria control is shot through with externalities—situations in which the actions of each player affects others (positively or negatively), and no player has an incentive to take these spillovers into account. Because interactions among players are important, malaria control, elimination, and eradication are best analyzed using the tools of game theory. Previously, I have used these tools to explore eradication of vaccine-preventable diseases (Barrett 2003, 2006, 2010, and 2013; Barrett and Hoel 2007). Malaria, however, is much more complex—and, as we shall see, much more interesting.

2. Comparison with other diseases

Though the earlier effort to eradicate malaria failed, the campaign to eradicate smallpox succeeded spectacularly (smallpox eradication being certified in 1979), and the latter success has had a more enduring and bewitching effect on global public health policy discussions than the former failure. If we succeeded with smallpox, why not eradicate other diseases? The leaders of the smallpox campaign seem to have anticipated this reaction, for in the final chapter of their comprehensive account of that effort, they offer this warning:

“Disease eradication is unquestionably an attractive goal, but the difficulty of its achievement should not be underestimated. It must be borne in mind that when the smallpox eradication programme began, the prospects for its success were more favourable than for any other disease eradication programme that might be envisaged today. The technical feasibility of interrupting the transmission of the smallpox virus had already been demonstrated both in the industrialized countries and in many developing ones; an inexpensive, highly effective vaccine was available; and there was a substantial political commitment to the achievement of the goal that had been set. Nevertheless, however favorable the circumstances, success was by no means a certainty even during the concluding years or even the final months of the programme. Indeed, the gap between success and failure in a number of national programmes was a narrow one, and the issue was often favourably decided by fortuitous and unpredictable political developments and with only marginally adequate resources. It is difficult to conceive of other disease

eradication programmes experiencing fewer problems; and if they were technically more difficult or less adequately and universally supported, their success would appear to be doubtful indeed (Fenner et al. 1988: 1366).”

Notwithstanding the obstacles, after smallpox was eradicated, the world embarked on two other eradication efforts: one for polio, a disease that, like smallpox, poses a global threat; and one for Guinea worm, a disease that afflicts only poor people living in poor, tropical countries.

The World Health Assembly approved the goal to eradicate polio in 1988, pledging to achieve it by 2000. The program succeeded spectacularly in reducing transmission; by 2000 there were only 719 confirmed cases worldwide. However, despite an ongoing effort, massive financial support, and a number of technical adaptations, the goal of zero cases remains just out of reach even now. Last year, there were 22 cases of wild polio (and 91 cases of circulating vaccine-derived polio). The program may eventually succeed, but the difficulty of reducing the case count to zero worldwide is enormous. Just last week, a mother-daughter team of polio vaccinators was assassinated in Pakistan.³

The effort to eradicate Guinea worm, approved by the World Health Assembly in 1991, is also close to its final goal. In 2017, there were only 30 cases worldwide. However, this program recently discovered that dogs as well as people host *Dracunculus medinensis*, and so now, to succeed, dogs as well as people must be cut out of the Guinea worm’s lifecycle. The polio and Guinea worm eradication campaigns may yet succeed, but their struggles should reinforce the warning that eradication is an enterprise fraught with difficulties.

Table 1 compares all of these previous efforts, the one success, the one big failure, and the two ongoing initiatives. Three differences between malaria and the other diseases stand out. First, malaria has an R_0 that varies dramatically from place to place, with a very high upper value.⁴ Malaria may not be harder to eliminate than smallpox or polio in low transmission areas, but in high transmission areas malaria will be a formidable adversary. Second, all the main tools for fighting malaria are prone to resistance, and this wasn’t a concern of the other eradication efforts. Finally, there are more tools available for fighting malaria than the other pathogens. The previous effort to eradicate malaria relied almost exclusively on insecticide spraying using DDT, and failed at least in part because mosquitoes developed resistance to DDT.

Smallpox was transmitted person-to-person and eradicated using a vaccine. Polio is also transmitted person-to-person and its demise is being pursued using a vaccine. A

³ See Donald G. McNeil Jr., “Killings Shake Pakistan’s Polio Eradication Drive,” *New York Times*, 23 January 2018, p. D3.

⁴ R_0 , the basic reproductive number for a disease, is the number of secondary cases that result when a single infected person is introduced into a population in which all people are susceptible. This value must exceed one in order for a disease to spread.

vaccine protects individuals who are vaccinated. However, it also offers a measure of protection to the people who are not vaccinated. This gives rise to an interior Nash equilibrium in which some people are vaccinated and some are not and the disease continues to circulate (Barrett 2013). Elimination of either disease from a jurisdiction thus requires public policy interventions.

Malaria is different. Malaria is transmitted via a vector, the *Anopheles* mosquito, and there is no vaccine (currently) that can control it. Instead, malaria is controlled by reducing breeding sites, killing the larvae, killing adult mosquitoes (indoor spraying and insecticide-treated bed nets), preventing individuals from being bitten (bed nets and changes to the housing stock), and suppressing the disease in infected persons using antimalarial drugs and blocking transmission to susceptible persons. In this paper, I focus on the use of bed nets and drugs, both for treatment and for reducing transmission..

Table 1
Comparison of Eradication Efforts

Disease	Smallpox	Polio	Guinea worm	Malaria
Pathogens	Variola major, variola minor	Wild (WPV) and circulating vaccine-derived (cVDPV) polioviruses 1, 2, and 3.	<i>Dracunculus medinensis</i>	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> , <i>P. vivax</i> , <i>P. ovale</i> , <i>P. malariae</i>
Eradication program	Approved by WHA, 1959; intensified program, 1967-1977.	Approved by World Health Assembly, 1988.	Begun in 1986; approved by WHA, 1991.	Approved by WHA, 1955.
Outcome	Declared eradicated by WHA, 1980.	WPV2 declared eradicated, 2015; WPV3 and cVDPV3 undetected for years; cVDPV1 last detected, 2016; cVDPV2 and WPV1 still circulate in a few countries.	As of late-2017, only 13 cases confirmed this year.	After encountering many problems, the WHA stepped back from eradication in 1969, favoring a strategy of control towards future eradication.
Non-human host	None. ⁵	None.	Dogs. ⁶	None. <i>P. knowlesi</i> has primate hosts. It infects, but is not transmitted by, humans.
Transmission	Human-to-human via face-to-face contact	Human-to-human via fecal-oral route	Via water containing Guinea worm larvae	Transmitted by about 40 different <i>Anopheles</i> mosquitoes.
Incubation period	10-15 days ³	7-12 days ³		7-30 days. ⁷
Latent period	8-11 days ³	1-3 days ³		9-16 days. ⁸
Infectious period	2-3 days ³	14-20 days ³		Up to around 300 days for <i>P. falciparum</i> . ³
Immunity post-infection	Yes	Yes	No	Repeated exposure needed to maintain immunity.
Basic reproductive number, R_0	3.5-6 ⁹	5-7 ³		1-3,000 ¹⁰

⁵ A related orthopoxvirus, monkeypox, is transmitted from animals to humans. Human-to-human transmission of this virus is difficult, and smallpox vaccine is effective in reducing transmission.

⁶ It was only recently discovered that dogs can be infected with Guinea worm and sustain the pathogen's life cycle.

⁷ <https://www.cdc.gov/malaria/about/disease.html>

⁸ Anderson and May (1991). Values depend on species and temperature.

⁹ Gani and Leach (2001).

¹⁰ Smith et al. (2007).

Table 1 (cont'd)
Comparison of Eradication Efforts

Disease	Smallpox	Polio	Guinea worm	Malaria
Case fatality rate	20% or more for variola major ¹¹	0.01-0.025%	0%	0.2% ¹²
Spatial distribution	Global	Global	Regional	Global, with some regions being high transmission, some low, and some zero.
Methods of control	Vaccination	Vaccination	Filtering water and keeping infected people out of open water.	Insecticide-treated bed nets, indoor residual spraying, antimalarial drugs, larval source control. In future, perhaps vaccines and gene drive.
Resistance	None.	None.	None.	A problem for virtually all interventions.
Surveillance challenges	Few.	Only about 1 in 200 cases show symptoms. Confirmation of infection requires blood tests.	Various problems in poor, conflict-prone countries like South Sudan. ¹³	Asymptomatic malaria in low-transmission areas is difficult to detect.
International financing	Eradication effort nearly failed for a lack of funds.	Fund raising has been very successful.	Adequate.	Under funding contributed to the program's failure.
Post-eradication risks	Accidental release from labs; bioterrorism. Vaccine is stockpiled to guard against these risks.	Accidental release; bioterrorism, including from release of synthetic viruses; excretion of virus by immune-compromised individuals.	None that are known.	These risks need to be evaluated before eradication is attempted.
Economics of eradication	Benefit-cost ratio over 100:1. ¹⁴	Generally, favorable, though these analyses typically make optimistic assumptions. ¹⁵	Eradication "probably more cost-effective than control by the year 2030." ¹⁶	

¹¹ Fenner et al. (1988), p. 175.

¹² Calculated based on 429,000 deaths and 212 million cases in 2015; <http://www.who.int/features/factfiles/malaria/en/>.

¹³ Awofeso (2013).

¹⁴ Fenner et al. (1988: 1364-1366); Barrett (2013).

¹⁵ Duintjer Tebbens et al. (2010); see also Barrett (2013).

¹⁶ Fitzpatrick et al. (2017).

3. Basic epidemiological model

I begin with the simplest mathematical model of malaria transmission, the basic Ross-Macdonald model:¹⁷

$$\dot{X} = mabY(1 - X) - rX \quad (1.1)$$

$$\dot{Y} = acX(1 - Y) - gY, \quad (1.2)$$

where X is the proportion of humans with parasites, Y is the proportion of mosquitoes that are infectious, m is the number of (female) mosquitoes per human, a is the number of bites on a human per mosquito per day, b is the proportion of those bites that cause infection, c is the proportion of bites on an infectious human that cause a mosquito to be infected, r is the rate at which infection is cleared in humans, and g is the rate at which mosquitoes die (naturally).

It is as well to note here some of the limitations of this model. The model assumes that mosquitoes that bite infected humans are able to pass the infection on to other humans immediately, and yet it takes a number of days (the precise number depending, among other things, on temperature) for the gametocytes ingested by a mosquito to develop into sporozoites, the stage at which the parasite can be passed to humans, and in the interval some of the infected mosquitoes will die. The model assumes that biting by mosquitoes is random, when it is known that mosquitoes favor some individuals over others. The model assumes that all humans are equally able to transmit malaria, and yet people who are exposed to malaria repeatedly acquire immunity, suppressing transmission. This makes malaria control in high transmission areas a very different proposition from malaria control in low transmission areas, but the distinction is lost in this model. The model assumes that people who are already infected cannot be infected by another parasite, when it is known that reinfection (a phenomenon known as “superinfection”) is common. The model assumes that there exists just one kind of parasite and a single kind of vector, when there are different species of parasite, each with its own transmission features, and even more species of vector, each with its own preferences for biting.

The advantage of models that abstract from details is that they can yield insights that are easily understood. More complex models may be more realistic in some respects, but they also tend to be harder to understand. And no mathematical model can truly represent the realities of something as complex as global malaria eradication.

Solving for the steady state rates of prevalence for mosquitoes and humans, we get

¹⁷ For a history of the origins and subsequent developments of this model, see Smith et al. (2012). The version of the model used here is particularly simple; see Anderson and May (1992).

$$\bar{X} = \frac{(R_0 - 1)}{R_0 + ac/g}, \bar{Y} = \frac{(R_0 - 1)ac/g}{R_0(1 + ac/g)}. \quad (1.3)$$

Figure 1a illustrates a steady state ($\dot{X} = \dot{Y} = 0$) in which malaria persists and Figure 1b a situation in which malaria is eliminated. Elimination requires that the slope of the $\dot{Y} = 0$ line exceed the slope of the $\dot{X} = 0$ line at $X, Y = 0$. It is easy to show that this requires

$$R_0 < 1, \quad (1.4)$$

where R_0 denotes the basic reproductive number for malaria—the number of secondary cases arising from a single infected human being introduced into a population in which all people are susceptible—determined from (1.1)-(1.2) as

$$R_0 = \frac{ma^2bc}{rg}. \quad (1.5)$$

R_0 is a parameter representing transmission in a “state of nature”—that is, in the absence of human efforts to control malaria. For many diseases, the basic reproductive number will be a fixed number, applying equally to every jurisdiction and being invariant over time.¹⁸ Malaria is different. The basic reproductive number for malaria ranges from one to over 3,000 (Smith et al 2007), depending on such differences as vector ecology and human density.¹⁹ Malaria transmission also changes with ecological disturbance such as deforestation (Guerra, Snow, and Hay 2006).

¹⁸ Of course, R_0 is known to vary for different diseases. Measles is transmitted more rapidly in urban areas. Polio is transmitted more easily in places with poor sanitation. As a general matter, however, the spatial variation in R_0 is small for most diseases, and is usually ignored.

¹⁹ As Smith et al (2007) note, it is difficult to compare the R_0 for malaria to other diseases because of other differences, particularly the generation time of the pathogen.

In addition, we can expect that malaria's R_0 will fall over time as a consequence of secular, development-related trends, largely independent of malaria control policy, especially modernization of the housing stock (Tusting et al. 2017) and urbanization (Hay et al 2005). Indeed, it conceivable that the process of development may suffice to eliminate malaria in low transmission areas. It may even suffice to eradicate

malaria worldwide eventually. However, it is as well to emphasize that causation also runs the other way: malaria can be an impediment to development (Gallup and Sachs 2001). Indeed, the latter effect could be so strong as to create a situation in which there exist two social-ecological equilibria: one in which high malaria transmission prevents a country or region from developing; and another in which high development prevents malaria from being established. Additionally, even if the process of development would eventually cause malaria to be eliminated and perhaps even eradicated, there is a powerful case for accelerating this shift. As noted before, malaria kills hundreds of thousands of young children in sub-Saharan Africa and is a scourge in much of the world. Its elimination and eradication would save lives and improve lives.

Climate change is often mentioned as an amplifier of malaria transmission, but the effect of climate change on malaria is highly uncertain (Caminade et al. 2014). All else being equal, climate change will likely cause malaria to increase in some places and to decrease in others (Murdock, Sternberg, and Thomas 2016). These studies focus on the direct effects of climate change (higher temperatures and, in wetter areas, greater rainfall), but there may also be indirect effects. For example, if climate change stunts development, the positive trend noted above would be reversed. Similarly, climate change is expected to stimulate migration (Missirian and Schlenker 2017), which could also cause malaria may spread. According to Martens and Hall (2000: 103), migration undermined the previous eradication effort: “The movement of infected people from areas where malaria was still endemic to areas where the disease had been eradicated led to resurgence of the disease.”

4. Human interventions

Let R_c denote the reproductive number for malaria under a regime of *control* (as opposed to R_0 , which applies in a “state of nature”). Control may involve a combination of measures, including: (i) spraying of breeding sites with larvicides to reduce the number of mosquitoes, m ; (ii) use of bed nets to reduce the biting rate, a ; (iii) killing of adult mosquitoes, either through indoor spraying of insecticide or through the use of insecticide-treated bed nets, to increase g ; (iv) use of antimalarials by infected individuals, to speed their rate of recovery, r ; (v) use of chemoprophylaxis to prevent disease (and, possibly in the future, vaccines to block infection), lowering b ; and (vi) the use of drugs (and, possibly in the future, vaccines) to reduce transmission, c (in the future, gene-editing technology could reduce or eliminate the ability of mosquitoes to transmit malaria, lowering c and perhaps reducing it to zero).

Note from eq. (1.5) that an intervention that can reduce parameter a has a particularly powerful effect, as this is the only term in R_0 that is squared. Reducing a has a double effect, simultaneously reducing the chances that a susceptible mosquito and a susceptible person will become infected.

Note as well the contrast with vaccine-preventable diseases. For these diseases, control by means of mass vaccination obeys the relation, $R_c = (1-p)R_0$, where p

represents the fraction of the population that is immune. Reducing p is mathematically equivalent to reducing m , b , and c , and to increasing r and g , as changes in all of these parameter values have linear effects on R_c (reducing a , as noted previously, has an even more powerful effect). Since there are so many more ways to control malaria than to control smallpox or polio, malaria would seem to have an advantage for elimination and eradication. However, the opposite is closer to the truth. As noted before, the R_0 for malaria is exceptionally high in high transmission areas. Malaria elimination in these areas would require near perfection not only in the efficacy of combinations of interventions, but in their take up by a population.

To eliminate malaria in a region in which malaria is endemic ($R_0 > 1$) we must have $R_c < 1$. Let $\mathbf{v} = v(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$ denote the vector of possible inputs to malaria control. If no inputs are employed, we have $\mathbf{v}^0 = (0, 0, \dots, 0)$. No inputs implies $R_c = R_c(\mathbf{v}^0; R_0) = R_0$. By contrast, if each input is used to the maximum extent possible, we have $\mathbf{v}^{\max} = (v_1^{\max}, v_2^{\max}, \dots, v_n^{\max})$. Let $R_c^{\min} = R_c(\mathbf{v}^{\max}; R_0)$ denote the lowest effective reproductive number attainable in an area. For elimination to be feasible in areas for which $R_0 > 1$, we must have $R_c^{\min} < 1$. Currently, this condition is not believed to be satisfied in high transmission areas. This means that a belief that eradication can succeed is a belief that new and improved technologies will emerge as a consequence of the decision to pursue eradication.

What are the maximum reductions currently achievable? One study in Tanzania found that if the antimalarials being used at the time were replaced by the more effective artemisinin-based combination therapy, prevalence would fall by at most one-half, with the largest impact (in percentage terms) being in low-transmission areas (Okell et al. 2008). To reduce transmission further, clearly other interventions would be needed. (Expand on this paragraph.)

In the future, this could change. For reasons mentioned previously, progress in development should help. New tools may also help. Examples include drugs or vaccines that block infection or transmission, and CRISPR-edited mosquitoes that can eliminate the vector. At the same time, it's also possible that the situation could worsen—for example, by resistance undermining today's effective interventions.

My analysis below focuses on bed nets (both untreated and insecticide-treated) and drugs (taken both as a treatment and for prophylaxis). Analysis of indoor residual spraying would differ little from that of treated bed nets, as both interventions raise g , benefiting users and non-users alike (note as well that field evidence has yet to show whether one of these interventions is more effective than the other; see Shaukat, Bremen, and McKenzie 2010). I ignore indoor residual spraying in this paper.²⁰ (I could include this in a future draft.) I also ignore larval source

²⁰ From the perspective of behavior, the difference between these interventions, if any, would show only in a model of household choice. Indoor residual spraying benefits everyone in a household,

management, which includes environmental interventions like the draining of breeding areas and the application of larvicides. Larval management reduces the abundance of mosquito larvae, and is recommended only as a supplemental intervention. According to the WHO, it should only be used as a supplementary tool, and is mainly applicable in urban areas.

5. Bed nets

Use of bed nets is a private choice that has public consequences. A person who is fully protected by a bed net cannot pass malaria on to others: a positive externality that is akin to vaccination. Bed nets also have another effect, depending on the type of net. Untreated nets repel mosquitoes, causing them to bite unprotected persons: a negative externality. Insecticide treated bed nets, by contrast, kill mosquitoes, removing the negative externality of repellence.

Suppose that the mosquito vector feeds only on humans and only at night, when humans are sleeping. (This again is an assumption made for simplicity.) Suppose as well that a fraction ϕ of humans use bed nets and that a fraction $1 - \phi$ do not. Finally, suppose that bed nets offer users full protection. Then, in a steady state, a fraction ϕ of the population will be malaria-free; denoting protected persons by the subscript P , $\bar{X}_p = 0$.

I consider two scenarios. In the Repel scenario, bed nets repel but do not kill mosquitoes. In the Kill scenario, bed nets kill mosquitoes that attempt to bite protected persons. I further assume that effects are complete—that repellence and mosquito mortality are 100 percent. I also ignore related effects, such as the time it takes for a repelled mosquito to find an unprotected person and the probability that the mosquito will die in the search. For a more general formulation, see Birget and Koella (2015).²¹

If nets repel mosquitoes, the dynamics of infection among unprotected persons (denoted by the subscript U) can be described by

$$\dot{X}_U^R = \frac{mab}{(1-\phi)} Y^R (1 - X_U^R) - rX_U^R, \quad (1.6)$$

whereas treated bed nets benefit only the individuals who sleep under them. Bargaining within the household may be a subject worthy of future research, but I ignore it here.

²¹ Birget and Koella (2015) develop a much richer model than the one I present here, incorporating considerations such as the possibility that mosquitoes may target non-humans as well as humans; that they may bite humans outdoors as well as indoors; that repellence by nets may be imperfect; that the insecticide treatment may not kill all mosquitoes attempting to bite a protected person; and that mosquitoes may die in the course of searching for a person to bite, after failing to bite a human in their previous attempts.

where X_U^R denotes the fraction of unprotected persons who are infected in the Repel case and Y^R denotes the fraction of mosquitoes in the Repel case that are infectious. The parameter m is now divided by $(1-\phi)$ to remove protected persons from the denominator of mosquitoes per human.

If nets kill mosquitoes, infection among unprotected persons becomes

$$\dot{X}_U^K = mabY^K(1-X_U^K) - rX_U^K. \quad (1.7)$$

Eq. (1.7) resembles (1.1), though of course (1.7) is for unprotected persons only and (1.1) is for all persons. Note as well that ϕ does not appear in eq. (1.7). This is because treated bed nets reduce the number of mosquitoes and the population of humans able to become infected by or to transmit malaria by the same amount.

The dynamics of transmission to mosquitoes in the Repel case is given by

$$\dot{Y}^R = acX_U^R(1-Y^R) - gY^R. \quad (1.8)$$

For the killed case, the equivalent equation is

$$\dot{Y}^K = acX_U^K(1-Y^K) - \frac{gY^K}{(1-\phi)}. \quad (1.9)$$

Here, mortality of infected mosquitoes increases as a proportion of these mosquitoes will be killed when they alight upon a treated net.

Eq. (1.8) implies that bed nets do not have a direct effect on transmission among mosquitoes in the Repel case. But by (1.6) they do have an indirect effect, by increasing X_U^R . This effect is illustrated in Figure 2a. In the Kill case, these effects are reversed. Eq. (1.7) implies that bed nets do not have a direct effect on prevalence in the population of unprotected persons. However, by (1.9) they do have an indirect effect; by lowering Y^K , bed nets cause prevalence in unprotected persons, X_U^K , to fall. This is shown in Figure 3a.

Solving for the steady states, and noting that $\bar{X}^R = (1-\phi)\bar{X}_U^R + \phi\bar{X}_P^R$ and $\bar{X}^K = (1-\phi)\bar{X}_U^K + \phi\bar{X}_P^K$, we have:

$$\bar{X}^R = \frac{(1-\phi)[R_0 - (1-\phi)]}{(R_0/(1-\phi) + ac/g)}, \quad \bar{Y}^R = \frac{R_0 - (1-\phi)}{(R_0 + abm/r)} \quad (1.10)$$

and

$$\bar{X}^K = \frac{R_0(1-\phi)-1}{R_0+ac/g}, \bar{Y}^K = \frac{R_0(1-\phi)-1}{R_0[(1-\phi)+g/ac]}. \quad (1.11)$$

Let ϕ_c denote the critical level of bed net use—the level at which prevalence in the human population falls to zero, the elimination level. From (1.10) we see that $\phi_c^R = 1$, whereas from (1.11) $\phi_c^K = 1 - 1/R_0$, a value identical to the level of vaccination needed to eliminate a vaccine-preventable disease (Anderson and May 1991). In the Kill case, the use of treated bed nets brings about a kind of “herd immunity,” so that elimination can be achieved with less than 100% coverage.

Figures 2a and b show the effect of increased bed net use in the Repel case. As shown in Fig. 2a, prevalence among both unprotected individuals and mosquitoes increase. The former effect is due to more mosquitoes targeting unprotected persons. The latter effect is more indirect. Prevalence in mosquitoes increases because prevalence in the human population on which the mosquitoes feed increases. As shown in Fig. 2b, prevalence in the general human population declines overall.

Figures 3a and 3b show the effect of increased bed net use in the Kill case. Fig. 3a shows that higher bed net use reduces prevalence in mosquitoes, offering a measure of protection even to people who are not using a bed net. Fig 3b shows that, in the population as a whole, the use of insecticide treated nets reduces prevalence significantly, as the direct effect of protecting net users is magnified by the additional effect of protecting non-users.

From these equations, it can be shown that $\bar{X}(0) > \bar{X}^R(\bar{\phi}) > \bar{X}^K(\bar{\phi})$ and $\bar{Y}^R(\bar{\phi}) > \bar{Y}(0) > \bar{Y}^K(\bar{\phi})$ for all $\bar{\phi} > 0$. Prevalence among mosquitoes is increased by repellency, as under our assumptions mosquitoes are directed to feed on a human population having a higher prevalence. As noted by Killeen and Smith (2007: 868), “it is theoretically possible that interventions that divert rather than kill mosquitoes could even increase the stability of malaria transmission by increasing vectorial capacity in the most intense foci of transmission.”

Treated nets thus help the most to reduce malaria in humans—assuming that ϕ is given. But of course ϕ is not given. It reflects the choices that humans make. I turn to this next.

Fig. 2a

Fig. 2b

Fig. 3a

Fig. 3b

6. The game theory of bed net adoption

How is ϕ determined? The mathematical epidemiology literature takes ϕ to be exogenous. Here I model ϕ as arising from private choices.

In deciding whether to use a bed net, an individual will take the choices made by others as given. Suppose k other people use bed nets. Then, if i doesn't use a bed net, $\phi = k/N$ (if i uses a bed net $\phi = (k + 1)/N$).

6.1 Repel

In the Repel scenario, given that the bed net is assumed to provide complete protection, i 's payoff to using a net is $\pi_i^R(1) = -c^R$, where c^R is the cost of using the bed net, and i 's payoff to not using a net is $\pi_i^R(0) = -Bbma\bar{Y}^R$, where $bma\bar{Y}^R$ is the force of infection—the probability that an unprotected person will be infected—and B is the private cost of becoming infected.

The value of B can be interpreted as the willingness to pay to avoid infection. This value can be estimated directly, by asking people questions that reveal their willingness to pay (see the meta-analysis by Trapero-Bertran et al. 2013). A different approach is to estimate the benefits of avoided infections from empirically. For example, a study of malaria elimination efforts in the United States around 1920 and in Brazil, Colombia, and Mexico around 1955 found that the interventions increased incomes and literacy of the individuals born after this time (Bleakley 2010). Similarly, Barofsky, Anekwe, and Chase (2015) found that, in Uganda, the malaria eradication campaign over the years 1959-1960 “raised educational attainment by about a half year for both males and females, increased primary school completion among females and generated an almost 40% rise in the likelihood of male wage employment.” Effects such as these are likely to be capitalized in the value of B , but it is to be expected that B will in addition reflect other considerations.

It pays an individual to use a bed net if $\pi_i^R(1; k) \geq \pi_i^R(0; k)$. We know $\pi_i^R(1; k) = -c^R$. We also know $\pi_i^R(0; k) = -\Phi(k)$ where

$$\Phi(k) = \frac{Bbma[R_0 - (1 - k/N)]}{(R_0 + abm/r)}. \quad (1.12)$$

Using the above inequality gives:

Proposition 1. *In a society for which malaria is present and the only protection available is an untreated bed net, there are three possibilities: (i) if $\Phi(0) > c^R$, then there exists a unique Nash equilibrium in which all persons use bednets, malaria is eliminated, and this outcome is efficient; (ii) if $c^R > \Phi(N - 1)$, then there exists a unique Nash equilibrium in which no one uses a bednet, malaria transmission persists, and this outcome is efficient; and (iii) if $\Phi(N - 1) > c^R > \Phi(0)$, then there exist two Nash equilibria (in pure strategies), in one of which no one uses a bed net and malaria*

persists, and in the other of which everyone uses a bed net and malaria is eliminated, with only this second equilibrium being efficient.

The proposition is illustrated in Figure 4a. The vertical axis shows payoffs. The horizontal axis shows the number of other persons using bed nets. The solid horizontal line represents the right hand side of (1.12) and the upward sloping lines represent different parameter configurations of the left hand side of (1.12). As shown in the figure, there are three qualitatively different situations. If the lowest upward sloping curve represents the left hand side of (1.12), there exists a unique Nash equilibrium in which no individuals use bed nets and this is efficient. If the highest upward sloping curve represents the left hand side of (1.12), there exists a unique Nash equilibrium in which all individuals use a bed net, and this is efficient. Finally, if the upward sloping line in the middle of the figure represents the left hand side of (1.12), then there exist two Nash equilibria (in pure strategies), one in which no one uses a bed net and one in which everyone uses a bed net. Here, only the latter equilibrium is efficient. To be sure that a community settles on this equilibrium rather than the former one requires coordination.

Fig. 4a

An interesting implication of this analysis is that, if untreated bed nets are available and their use is efficient, very little (if any) public intervention is required to encourage people to use them. The reason is that, if I sleep under an untreated bed net, I impose a negative externality on my neighbors, increasing the incentive *they*

have to sleep under an untreated bed net. By contrast, if I get vaccinated, I impose a positive externality on my neighbors, decreasing the incentive they have to get vaccinated. According to the model, if elimination is efficient, its realization should be straightforward. But of course the model makes many simplifying assumptions, such as that mosquitoes feed exclusively on humans, that they do so only at night, and that bed nets offer complete protection to the persons who sleep under them.

It is interesting to compare the insights from this game theoretic model with that of a classical epidemiological model. Birget and Koella (2015: 11) also find that untreated bed nets create a negative externality, but they conclude that, “at the community level, repellency may be detrimental for the control of malaria,” whereas I find that repellency is a boon for malaria control. The reason for the contrast is that Birget and Koella fix the level of take-up of untreated bed nets, whereas in my model this level is determined endogenously.

6.2 Kill

It pays to use a treated bed net if $\pi_i^K(1;k) \geq \pi_i^K(0;k)$. We know that $\pi_i^K(1;k) = -c^K$, where c^K denotes the private cost of using a treated bed net ($c^K > c^R$).²²

It can further be shown that $\pi_i^K(0;k) = -\Psi(k)$, where

$$\Psi(k) = \frac{Bbma}{R_0} \left\{ \frac{R_0(1-k/N) - 1}{\left[(1-k/N) + g/ac \right]} \right\}. \quad (1.13)$$

As $-\Psi(k)$ denotes the payoff to not using a bed net, $\Psi(k)$ represents the benefit (harm avoided) of using a bed net. Intuitively, then, an individual is better off using a bed net than not using one if $\Psi(k) > c^K$. The relationship is shown in Fig. 4b.

²² A bed net costs approximately \$7.50, and treatments cost about \$2.50 each year (Guyatt and Snow 2002). Assuming that nets last three years, the annual cost of a treated net would be about twice that of an untreated net.

Fig. 4b

In contrast to the Repel scenario, in Kill the use of a treated bed net confers a positive externality. (The payoff curves to using a bed net slope downwards, not upwards as in Fig. 4a.) As shown in Fig. 4b, as more and more people sleep under a treated bed net, the incentive for the remaining people to sleep under a treated bed net declines.

Proposition 2a. *In a Nash equilibrium, so long as $c^K > 0$, use of treated bed nets will not eliminate malaria.*

Proof. *Making (1.13) an equality and solving for ϕ gives the Nash equilibrium take up rate*

$$\phi_K^* = \frac{Bbma(1 - 1/R_0) - c^K(1 + g/ac)}{Bbma - c^K}. \quad (1.14)$$

The proposition says that $\phi_K^ < \phi_K^c$. Proof by contradiction therefore requires $\phi_K^* \geq \phi_K^c$. Upon substituting, this condition requires $1/R_0 + g/ac \leq 0$, which is false.*

Is this Nash equilibrium efficient? Intuitively, it won't be efficient, because of the externality associated with its use—a positive benefit that each user will disregard. It is easy to show that the social benefit to using a treated bed net is $\Psi^{FC}(k)$, where

$$\Psi^{FC}(k) = \frac{Bbma}{R_0} \left[\frac{R_0(1-\phi)[(1-\phi) + 2g/ac] - g/ac}{[(1-\phi) + g/ac]^2} \right]. \quad (1.15)$$

As shown in Fig. 4b, the social benefit to incremental adoption of a treated bed net always exceeds the private benefit.

Proposition 2b. *The Nash equilibrium is inefficient. In the full cooperative outcome, more people would sleep under treated bed nets than in the Nash equilibrium. The efficient outcome can be achieved by subsidizing bed nets by the amount s^* , where $s^* = \Psi^{FC}(\phi^{FC}) - \Psi(\phi^{FC})$.*

As shown in Fig 4b, a subsidy of the amount s^* will cause people in a Nash equilibrium to purchase and use bed nets to the level $\phi^{FC} = k^{FC}/N$.

The private marginal benefit of adoption equals zero where $\phi = \phi^c$, where the superscript c denotes the critical level of adoption (analogous to the critical level of immunization for a vaccine-preventable disease). At this level of take up, the social marginal benefit of adoption also equals zero. The social marginal benefit of adoption becomes kinked at this critical level.

Let

$$\omega = \frac{Bbma}{R_0(1/R_0 + g/ac)}. \quad (1.16)$$

Then we have

Proposition 2c. *Full cooperation (optimal control) requires elimination if and only if $c^K \leq \omega$.*

In Fig 4b, optimal control does not commend elimination, but it is easy to see that, if ω were sufficiently large (relative to c^K), it would pay a society to eliminate malaria by means of treated bed nets. It is easy to see from (1.16) that elimination is more likely to be optimal the larger is B, b, m, a , and r .

7. Drug treatment

Antimalarial drugs harm and kill malaria parasites, limiting infection and its associated illness. Upon first taking the drug, there is a lag, following which there is

an approximately log linear decline in parasitaemia. Here I assume that antimalarial drugs reduce transmission by speeding the rate of recovery, r . (Antimalarials may also provide a benefit to an infected person in reduced probability of superinfection, though as noted before I ignore this possibility in this paper.) In particular, I assume that, by taking an antimalarial drug, an infected person recovers at rate $\hat{r} > r$. Although an infected person may take a drug solely for personal reasons, doing so creates a social benefit, reducing transmission.

Drugs taken for treatment will not eliminate malaria in high transmission areas where a significant proportion of infections are transmitted by older children and adults. These individuals, exposed to repeated infection, acquire infection-immunity or premunition and are thus largely asymptomatic—and individuals who lack symptoms have no reason to take antimalarials. However, as transmission falls, premunition will recede, causing yet more people to seek treatment (White 2008). Hence, the assumption I make here that individuals do not acquire immunity from repeated exposure may matter less for elimination than for control.

There are a great many drugs and drug combinations that can be taken, and the effect will vary depending on the drug and the target parasite. Most antimalarials—including chloroquine, proguanil, mefloquine, doxycycline, and the artemisinin-based combination therapies—kill the parasite after it has left the liver and entered the bloodstream. These drugs are particularly effective in providing protection from *P. falciparum* malaria. Others, like malarone and primaquine, kill the parasite in the liver as well as in the blood. These provide protection from *P. vivax*. My analysis is blind to such distinctions.

Suppose that a fraction θ of infected persons take the drug, and let $\bar{r} = (1 - \theta)r + \theta\hat{r}$. Then (1.1) becomes

$$\dot{X} = mabY(1 - X) - \bar{r}X \quad (1.17)$$

and the basic reproductive number becomes

$$\bar{R}_0(\theta) = \frac{ma^2bc}{\bar{r}(\theta)g}. \quad (1.18)$$

The effect of drug treatment is shown in Fig. 5. Note the similarity to Fig. 3b. The reason is that the interventions underlying each figure have similar qualitative effects. Use of insecticide treated nets increases g , whereas use of antimalarial drugs for treatment increases r . Both interventions lower the basic reproductive number with intervention.

Fig. 5

8. The game theory of drug treatment

I assume here that drug use is based on rational calculation, but human behavior can be complex. For example, people are known to take antimalarial drugs when they have a fever, even after a diagnostic test shows them to be malaria-free (Cohen et al. 2015). It is also common for people to stop taking a drug after they feel better and before the full course has been completed. Behavior is highly variable. In particular, it can vary systematically between high and low transmission areas, between urban and rural areas, between men and women, and from one country and society to another (McCombie 1996). Note, however, that some behaviors that are unhelpful to malaria control are consistent with individual rationality. Many people who show symptoms will delay seeking treatment and, if their symptoms persist or worsen, take a drug without consulting a health professional, partly if not largely because of the cost of traveling to a clinic. The private cost of treatment is a primary consideration in peoples' take-up of an effective drug.

As before, the private cost of infection is represented by the parameter B . If the treatment drug is efficacious, the cost of a bout of malaria will be lower when the infection is treated. Denote this cost by \hat{B} ; $\hat{B} < B$.

How to estimate \hat{B} ? It could be estimated directly, using the same approaches as have been employed to estimate B . Trapero-Bertran et al. (2013) carry out a meta-regression analysis of data taken from a variety of different studies, and obtain a mean willingness to pay of \$1.03 for insecticide-treated nets and \$0.91 for malaria treatment (both values in 2011 US dollars).²³ However, it's hard to know how to interpret these values. For example, the paper does not comment on the respondents' beliefs about the efficacy of these different interventions, and these beliefs could easily vary from study to study.²⁴

If infected person i does not take the drug, he or she gets the payoff $\pi_i^D(0) = -B$. If i takes the drug, he or she gets $\pi_i^D(1) = -c^D - \hat{B}$. Person i can thus be expected to take the drug provided $-c^D - \hat{B} \geq -B$. Note that c^D includes not only the purchase price of the drug, but the cost of seeking treatment, which can involve substantial travel for some people. It also includes the side effects, which can be serious (Taylor and White 2004). From the above, we get:

Proposition 3a. *In a Nash equilibrium either no infected persons seek treatment ($\theta = 0$) or all infected persons seek treatment ($\theta = 1$). In the latter case, malaria will be eliminated if and only if $\bar{R}_0(1) = ma^2bc/\hat{r}g \leq 1$.*

When an infected person takes the drug, he or she not only recovers more quickly (a private benefit); he or she also transmits malaria for a shorter interval of time (a social benefit). Of course, individuals are unlikely to take the latter effect into account when deciding whether or not to seek treatment. If, in the Nash equilibrium, $\theta = 1$, then individual behavior will be efficient. However, if, in the Nash equilibrium, $\theta = 0$, then individual behavior may be inefficient; society would be better off if infected persons obtained treatment, but such persons have no incentive to do so.

Proposition 3b. *The Nash equilibrium in which no infected person seeks treatment ($\theta = 0$) is inefficient if and only if*

²³ For given estimation technique and values of variables such as income and education.

²⁴ Rather than estimate \hat{B} directly, upon making certain assumptions we can infer its value. Think of B as representing the integral of utility loss (relative to a state of wellness) over the duration of infection. Taking the per-period cost of infection, \bar{B} , to be a constant, and assuming that this value is the same, whether or not an individual receives treatment, we get $B = \int_0^\infty \bar{B}e^{-rt} dt$ and $\hat{B} = \int_0^\infty \bar{B}e^{-\hat{r}t} dt$, which implies $\hat{B} = Br/\hat{r}$. In short, the cost of malaria when treated is proportional to the cost of malaria when untreated, with the constant of proportionality reflecting the relative rates of recovery (time discounting would add another term). Put simply, a drug treatment that doubles the rate of recovery halves the cost of infection.

$$\hat{B} - B > -c^D \geq \hat{B} - B \left[\frac{(ma^2bc - rg)}{(ma^2bc - \hat{r}g)} \right]. \quad (1.19)$$

When (1.19) is satisfied, the efficient outcome in which all infected persons take the drug can be supported as a Nash equilibrium if the price of the drug is subsidized by an amount s_D^* , where

$$s_D^* = \hat{B} + c^D - B. \quad (1.20)$$

This subsidy will cause malaria to be eliminated if and only if $\bar{R}_0(1) = ma^2bc/\hat{r}g \leq 1$.

Proof. The strict inequality on the LHS of (1.19) guarantees that $\theta = 0$ is a Nash equilibrium. The weak inequality on the RHS of (1.19) is the condition guaranteeing that $\theta = 1$ in the full cooperative outcome. To see this, note that, if no one uses the drug, in the steady state the aggregate payoff will equal $\Pi(\theta = 0) = -Bbma\bar{Y}N$, where \bar{Y} is given by (1.3), whereas if all infected persons take the drug, the aggregate payoff will equal $\Pi(\theta = 1) = (-c^T - \hat{B})bma\bar{Y}^D N$, where

$$\bar{Y}^D = \frac{[\bar{R}_0(1) - 1]ac/g}{\bar{R}_0(1)(1 + ac/g)}. \quad (1.21)$$

The RHS of (1.19) is found by substitution.

9. Mass drug administration

Used for prevention rather than for treatment, antimalarial drugs are akin to vaccines. Travelers routinely take antimalarials as a protective measure. Often, pregnant women in malaria endemic areas are given these drugs, to protect them, their fetuses, and their newborn babies. Why, then, are anti-malarials not taken routinely for prophylaxis in malaria endemic areas? Greenwood (2010) argues that a primary reason is cost: not only the cost of purchasing and delivering the drug, but the cost to the individual of taking the drug.²⁵ “Any drug used for prophylaxis in large

²⁵ Greenwood (2010) distinguishes between cost and “acceptability,” the latter reflecting the cost to the individual of taking the drug, including the unpleasantness of the taste and side effects. My definition of “cost” incorporates both considerations. Greenwood gives other reasons for why anti-malarials aren’t taken more often for prophylaxis in endemic areas, including “sustainability,” resistance, and loss of immunity. However, loss of immunity is only a problem if an individual stops taking the drug, and so can be considered another cost to the individual of taking the drug. Resistance is more of a social than a private concern, and isn’t unique to the use of antimalarials for prophylaxis. Finally, the failure of any program to be sustained over time is an outcome to be explained rather than a reason for why drugs for prophylaxis aren’t taken in the first place.

populations,” Greenwood (2010: 3) says, “must be well tolerated as well as safe and few anti-malarials meet both of these criteria.”

Mass drug administration “consists of the administration of a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine (irrespective of the presence of symptoms or infection) to every member of a defined population or person living in a defined geographical area...at approximately the same time and often at repeated intervals” (WHO 2017: 1). This, anyway, is the ideal; as a practical matter, it is impossible for a program to guarantee 100% coverage. According to the WHO’s field manual, for mass drug administration to be effective in eliminating malaria,

“a very high proportion, generally *more than 80% of the targeted population* must be reached during the campaign.... This requires a *high level of community participation and engagement*. It is not enough to reach the majority of the population with distribution: coverage will be effective only if the number of people in the community who *correctly complete the full course* of antimalarial treatment is adequate. To achieve this, the population must accept the intervention and be willing to take the medicine as prescribed” (WHO 2017: 1).

Here, my focus is mainly on the last sentence of this prescription: the incentives for individuals to participate in mass drug administration.

Mass drug administration is intended to have two effects. First, and as in the analysis above, it accelerates the clearance of parasites in infected persons, increasing r . As we have already seen, this has an indirect effect in reducing transmission. Second, and unlike the preceding analysis, administration of the drug to susceptible persons reduces the chances they will become infected when bitten by an infectious mosquito, lowering b . This is a direct effect in reducing transmission. (There may also be an effect in lowering c , reflecting the chances that a susceptible mosquito will become infected when feeding on an infected person. I can explore this in future work.)

It should be noted that the effects of mass drug administration are uncertain (Okell et al., 2011). There have not been any randomized control trials of mass drug administration; the studies that exist cannot isolate the effect of mass drug administration from confounding factors, especially vector control. Moreover, the effect of mass drug administration using different drugs is unknown (Okell et al. 2011). Finally, although not studied here, widespread application of a drug would increase the chances of the emergence of drug resistance.²⁶

Partly for this reason, mass drug administration is not being considered as a permanent intervention. According to the WHO (2017: ix), mass drug administration “should be viewed as a time-limited intervention with specific targets for when it

²⁶ White (2017) maintains that this risk is low because persons who have asymptomatic malaria also have low parasite numbers.

should be discontinued, defined before implementation.” In particular, the WHO (2017: 2) says that mass drug administration can be considered “for the elimination of *P. falciparum* malaria... in areas approaching interruption of transmission where there is good access to treatment, effective implementation of vector control and surveillance, and a minimal risk of re-introduction of infection.” It should be noted that this is very different from the role mass vaccination has played in previous eradication efforts. Mass vaccination for polio, for example, has been maintained worldwide at least since 2000, and yet eradication has yet to be achieved.

Fig. 6, shows the effect of applying mass drug administration to a proportion θ of the population, the same fraction of infected persons being given the drug in Fig. 5. Fig. 6 thus shows the additional effect of mass drug administration over treatment. Note that the effect of mass drug administration will depend on many considerations. A review of mass drug administration by Newby et al. (2015) underlines the most important of these: choice of drug (artemisinin combination therapies and primaquine are particularly good at reducing transmission); delivery implementation (directly observed treatment being particularly important); the degree of coverage (not surprisingly, interruption of transmission requires high coverage); and community acceptance. As Fig. 6 is drawn, mass drug administration does not eliminate malaria. However, it is easy to see that the figure could have been drawn such that mass drug administration does have that effect. Whether this is possible—whether mass drug administration can reduce the effective reproductive number can be reduced below one—depends on θ , \hat{r} , and \hat{b} . The values of \hat{r} and \hat{b} are determined by the efficacy of the drug in relation to the target species of parasite. Further drug development can perhaps improve efficacy, but here I shall take these values as given. The value of θ is different; this value is subject to choice, the object of my analysis below.

Fig. 6

The incentive for infected persons to take the drug is unchanged from before. This is because their decision to take the drug won't be affected by whether others take the drug (given the assumption that behavior is guided by self-interest). Here I assume that these individuals wouldn't seek treatment in the absence of mass drug administration. Hence, mass drug administration achieves two purposes: it clears parasites in infected persons and it provides prophylaxis for susceptible persons. From here, my analysis focuses on the latter effect of mass drug administration.

By taking the drug, a susceptible person obtains the expected benefit, $B\bar{b}(\theta)ma\bar{Y}^M(\theta)$. Assume for simplicity that the cost of taking the drug is the same for a susceptible and an infected person, c^D .²⁷ Substituting for $\bar{Y}^M(\theta)$, it will pay an individual to take the drug as prophylaxis if and only if

$$B \frac{[ma^2\bar{b}(\theta)c - \bar{r}(\theta)]}{g+ac} \geq c^D. \quad (1.22)$$

²⁷ More importantly, the value of c^D would almost certainly be different for mass drug administration than for treatment of confirmed cases, because the drug combination used would be different. For example, mass drug administration would typically employ a partner drug (such as piperaquine) with a long half-life in an artemisinin-based combination therapy (Cheah and White 2016).

Substituting now for \bar{b} and \bar{r} , relation (1.22) becomes

$$\frac{B}{(g+ac)} \left\{ gr(R_0 - 1) - \theta \left[ma^2c(b - \hat{b}) + g(\hat{r} - r) \right] \right\} \geq c^D. \quad (1.23)$$

The term in brackets is a positive constant. Hence, the incentive for a susceptible individual to participate in a mass drug administration program falls linearly as more others participate.

Denoting the left hand side of (1.23) by the function $\Omega(\theta)$, the decision facing susceptible individuals is illustrated in Fig. 7. The figure shows payoffs and Nash equilibria for different sets of parameter values. The downward sloping curves represent Ω . The one with the positive and higher intercept on the right hand side is for parameter values \tilde{b} and \tilde{r} . The one with the negative and lower intercept on the right hand side is for parameter values $\tilde{\tilde{b}}$ and $\tilde{\tilde{r}}$, where $\tilde{\tilde{b}} < \tilde{b}$ and $\tilde{\tilde{r}} > r$. Hence, relative to the upper curve, this lower curve represents use of a more effective drug. One consequence of the difference in the effectiveness of the drugs employed is that the more effective drug is able to eliminate malaria and the less effective drug is not.

To see this, note that

$$\Omega(\theta) = 0 \Rightarrow \theta = \theta^c, \text{ where } \theta^c = \frac{1}{1 - \left[\hat{r}(\hat{R}_0 - 1) / r(R_0 - 1) \right]}. \quad (1.24)$$

In (1.24), θ^c denotes the critical level of mass drug administration needed to eliminate malaria. This critical level is 100% coverage if $\hat{R}_0 = 1$ and less than this if $\hat{R}_0 < 1$. In Fig. 7, elimination is only feasible for the more effective drug.

Proposition 4a. *Mass drug administration can eliminate malaria from a region in which $R_0 > 1$ if and only if $\hat{R}_0 = ma^2\hat{b}c/\hat{r}g \leq 1$. Elimination requires reaching a fraction θ^c of the population, where θ^c is given by (1.24).*

Fig. 7

Fig. 7 also shows various Nash equilibria. The parameter c_H^D represents the cost of a “high cost” drug. At this cost, there is a unique Nash equilibrium in which $\theta^{NE} = 0$, irrespective of the drug’s effectiveness (that is, irrespective of whether the parameters are \tilde{b} and \tilde{r} or $\tilde{\tilde{b}}$ and $\tilde{\tilde{r}}$). The reason is that, by assumption, both of the drugs depicted in the figure offer 100% protection to the persons who take them. The first person who contemplates taking the drug won’t care about the value of r or b , because once she takes the drug she will be at zero risk of getting infected, and that (by assumption) is all she cares about: her own self-interest.²⁸

The parameter c_L^D represents the cost of a “low cost” drug. At this cost, there are two Nash equilibria, both in the interior of Fig. 7. Perhaps surprisingly, the equilibrium level of coverage is higher for the less effective drug. The reason is that, for any $\theta > 0$, others’ usage of a drug reduces the risk of infection facing non-users by more when

²⁸ Note that, for infected persons, a difference in drug effectiveness could easily change the Nash equilibrium solved for in the previous section. A drug that is more effective at clearing the parasite would increase the value of \hat{B} . This drug might also be more expensive than the alternative, but if the difference between the benefit and cost were higher for this new drug, introduction of the drug could cause the Nash equilibrium to flip from no infected person taking the drug to all infected persons taking it.

the drug is more effective, reducing the incentive for susceptible persons to take the more effective drug. This is another powerful demonstration of the value of a game-theoretic analysis.

Note that I am looking here at mass drug administration in isolation of all other interventions. However, as noted before, the WHO's recommendation to apply mass drug administration is conditional on effective vector control. In this model, vector $s^* = c^D$. control can be interpreted as a reduction in m/g . It can be shown that $\partial\theta^c/\partial(m/g) > 0$, meaning that a higher level of vector control lowers the critical level of mass drug administration. The effect might be great enough to make elimination feasible even for a drug with properties \hat{b} and \hat{r} . Okell et al. (2011), using a dynamic, stochastic model, similarly find that mass drug administration is more likely to achieve local elimination when implemented in combination with stepped up vector control.

Fig. 7 looks remarkably similar to the game theory of private take-up of vaccines, with one important difference.²⁹ If a vaccine is fully protective to the individual, then the private benefit of vaccination intersects the horizontal axis strictly to the left of 100% coverage (thanks to herd immunity), meaning that elimination is achievable by mass vaccination. This was certainly the case for smallpox. It is also true for polio. The reason polio has not been eliminated worldwide is that it has been impossible to provide the needed coverage in just a few strongholds. Whether mass drug administration could eliminate malaria depends not only on coverage, but also on the effectiveness of the drugs in accelerating the clearance of parasites in infected persons and in providing prophylaxis in susceptible persons—and, as noted in the previous paragraph, the effectiveness of allied interventions, such as for vector control.

Proposition 4b. *In a Nash equilibrium, so long as $c^D > 0$, malaria will not be eliminated by individuals seeking prophylaxis. Mass drug administration can eliminate malaria if and only if $\hat{R}_0 \leq 1$ and individuals are offered a subsidy $s^* = c^D$.*

The subsidy eliminates the private cost of participating in a mass drug administration campaign. The concept of a “subsidy” here should be interpreted broadly. It can be interpreted as a set of inducements sufficient to make enough members of a community willing to take the drug that the threshold θ^c is just met.

A recent paper gives an indication of what a “subsidy” might consist of. In two villages in the Nog District, Savannakhet Province, Laos, 87% of the target population agreed

²⁹ Contrast Fig. 7 with Fig. 1 in Barrett (2013).

to participate in a mass drug administration campaign.³⁰ This is a substantial fraction, but the cost of achieving this participation rate must have been relatively high. According to Adhikari et al. (2018), the inducements given included: (i) a financial payment for participants' travel and opportunity costs; (ii) free primary health care; (iii) additional financial support to cover transport and hospitalization for individuals suffering from malaria or adverse events associated with taking the antimalarials; (iv) various gifts, including a set of cooking utensils, t-shirts printed with a malaria prevention message, and blankets; and (v) the installation of water pumps. Other factors included educating individuals about malaria and explaining the rationale for mass drug administration, and partnering with community members and health professionals in the locality in order to build trust. Unfortunately, it cannot be determined from the study the relative importance of these and other factors in determining participation. Moreover, the study does not give an estimate of the costs of the program.

The costs of participation can vary for a number of reasons. For example, in the case of *P. vivax*, elimination would require using primaquine, which poses a risk of haemolysis in individuals who are glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficient, a significant fraction of the population (Cheah and White 2016). Perceived risks are also important (Cheah and White 2016). According to a recent survey of experts (Kaehler et al. 2018: 5), perceptions have caused problems in the past: "in Cambodia, several people became ill after an MDA some years ago, and this prompted a strong aversion to MDA in local communities (and among policy makers). Stories of a death linked to an MDA in Myanmar had a similar impact." Social resistance to vaccines can be spotty, but as the polio eradication initiative has learned, such resistance in even a single locality can prevent elimination from being achieved. Elimination and especially eradication do not require that interventions like mass drug administration work pretty well in most places. They depend on such interventions working exceptionally well everywhere.

In keeping with my previous analyses, it is tempting to write the total payoff to a country of mass drug administration as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_M(\theta) = & -N \left\{ (1-\theta)B \left[\bar{X}^M(\theta) + \bar{b}(\theta)ma\bar{Y}^M(\theta)(1-\bar{X}^M(\theta)) \right] \right. \\ & \left. + \theta \left[(\hat{B} + c^D)\bar{X}^M(\theta) + c^D(1-\bar{X}^M(\theta)) \right] \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.25)$$

Within the curly brackets, there are four terms, separated by plus signs. Moving from left-to-right, the two terms in the first set of square brackets represent the payoffs to all infected persons and all susceptible persons, respectively, who do not get the drug;

³⁰ The target population excludes infants under 6 months of age, pregnant women, and severely ill people. Including these people in the denominator, participation reached 84% of the population.

and the two terms in the second set of square brackets represent the payoffs to all infected persons and all susceptible persons, respectively, who do get the drug.

Although it is tempting to write down this expression for the aggregate net benefits of mass drug administration, there are two problems with this formulation.

First, eq. (1.25) assumes that the marginal social cost of mass drug administration is the same as the marginal private cost, and the former cost will be larger. For example, the WHO recommends door-to-door distribution and directly observed treatment, and the social cost of this program would include both the costs borne by the agencies that carry it out and by individuals being given the drugs.

Second, and even more importantly, eq. (1.25) is a steady state representation of a policy to deploy mass drug administration. For any “interior” solution, it assumes ongoing intervention, which goes against the WHO policy of time-limited mass drug administration only in unusual circumstances, including as a component intervention for achieving local elimination. Eq. (1.25) is thus the wrong framework for considering the social net benefits of mass drug administration. This needs to be incorporated into a model of optimal elimination.

10. Next steps

In my next draft I intend to include a section looking at interactions among the various interventions, and a discussion of the optimal combinations of intervention for achieving elimination where this is feasible. I shall also provide a sketch of the economics of malaria elimination—again, where this is feasible.

The malaria eradication game would look very much like my previous analyses of vaccine-preventable diseases, for it involves a comparison of the payoffs countries get by controlling rather than eliminating malaria and an indication of the size of the “eradication dividend.” What will differ here are the numbers rather than the framework.

Two further analyses (at a minimum) should be undertaken, one involving the spatial aspects of malaria elimination/eradication and one involving the risk that elimination and eradication pose for the emergence of resistance.

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